

ARDIG D-2.2: Assessment of longitudinal studies and collection of necessary data.

Summary of WP3 questionnaire

Based on responses from 6 partners: IP (France), BfR (Germany), NVI (Norway), UCM (Spain), APHA (UK) and UoS (UK).

Collection of isolates

Source

- Human (UCM, IP, NVI, UoS): hospital/GP UTIs (IP, NVI, UoS), hospital blood bacteraemia (UoS), healthy (IP)
- Animal (UCM, BfR, NVI, APHA, UoS): healthy pigs (BfR, UoS, APHA), healthy cattle (BfR, UoS), healthy poultry (BfR, UoS, NVI), sick poultry (UoS), seagulls (APHA)
- Food (UCM, BfR, NVI): meat, milk and cheese (BfR), poultry meat (NVI)
- Environmental (UCM)

Species

- Enterobacteriaceae (all 6): mainly *E. coli* (all 6), some *Klebsiella* (IP, BfR, NVI)
- Pasteurellaceae (UCM)
- Identification methods: MALDI-TOF (BfR, NVI, UCM), CHROMagar/indole (UoS)

Focus

- AMR: ESBL⁺ (all 6), carbapenemase⁺ (IP, BfR, UoS, UCM), fluoroquinolone (BfR, APHA, UoS, UCM), colistin (BfR, UoS, UCM) and aminoglycoside resistance (UCM).
- MGEs: plasmids (IP-all, UCM-all, BfR-AMR⁺, NVI-IncK&I, UoS-AMR⁺), phages (BfR-AMR⁺), transposons (IP)

Methods of characterization

AMR profiling

- CLSI (BfR) / EUCAST (all 6)
- Kirby Bauer (IP, UoS, UCM) / E-TEST (IP, UCM) / MIC dilution (all 6)

AMR genes

- Multiplex PCR (BfR, NVI, UCM, UoS): *qnr* (BfR), *mcr* (BfR, UoS), ESBL (NVI, UoS), AmpC (NVI, UoS)
- PCR/Sanger sequencing (IP, BfR, NVI, UCM): ESBL (NVI)
- DNA hybridisation (BfR)
- qPCR (NVI): *blaCMY-2* (NVI)

- WGS-based (all 6): ResFinder (IP, BfR, NVI, UCM, UoS), APHA SeqFinderV3 (APHA), ARGannot (UoS), CARD (UoS), NCBI (UoS)

MGE type

- PCR-based replicon typing (BfR, NVI, UCM)
- Degenerate primer MOB typing (BfR, UCM)
- WGS-based (all 6): PlasmidFinder (IP, BfR, UCM, APHA, UoS), PHASTER/NCBI DB (BfR), BlastN/NCBI DB (BfR), IS Finder (BfR, APHA), PlasFlow (NVI)

Phylotype

- MLST (IP, UCM)
- Multiplex PCR (NVI, UCM)
- MLVA (NVI)
- PFGE (NVI)
- WGS-based (all 6): MLST (all 6), cgMLST (BfR), serotyping/CGE DB (BfR)

Virulence genes

- WGS-based (all 6): VirulenceFinder (BfR, NVI, UoS, UCM), MyDB finder/in house DB (BfR), SeqFinderV3/APHA virulence factor DB (APHA)

Whole genome sequencing

- Numbers: ~400 (IP), 100-200 (BfR), ~220 (NVI), some (UCM), 500+ (APHA), ~600 (UoS)
- Platform: Illumina (all 6), PacBio (IP-few, BfR), Nanopore (NVI-few, UCM, UoS-few)
- Quality control: IP pipeline (IP), FastQC (BfR, NVI, UCM, APHA), Shovill/quast (UoS)
- Assembly: SPAdes (all 6)
- Annotation: Prokka (IP, NVI, UCM, APHA, UoS), RAST (IP), PGAP (BfR)
- Phylogeny: ParSNP (IP, UoS), MEGA (IP), RAxML (IP, UCM, APHA), CSI phylogeny (BfR), Bionumerics (BfR)
- Pangenome analysis: Roary (IP, UCM, UoS)

Models of transmission/fitness

Fitness studies

- *In vitro* models (IP, BfR, NVI, UCM, UoS): *E. coli*/growth/survival/different media/sub-MIC (IP), *E. coli*/growth \pm *mcr*⁺ or *qnr*⁺ plasmids and phages (BfR), *E. coli*/plasmid competition/IncK and IncI plasmids (NVI), *E. coli*/gut models/AMR⁺ plasmids (UoS)
- *In vivo* models (UCM, UoS): *E. coli*/*Galleria mellonella*/AMR⁺ plasmids (UoS)

Transmission studies

- *In vitro* models (IP, BfR, NVI, UCM, UoS): *E. coli*/different lineages and sources/carbapenemase⁺ plasmids (IP), Enterobacteriaceae (esp. *E. coli*)/conjugation, mobilization, transposition, integration, lysogenization/AMR plasmids and phages (BfR), *E. coli*, *Serratia*, other Enterobacteriaceae/broth, solid, biofilm, different temperatures/IncK and IncI plasmids (NVI), *E. coli*/gut models/AMR⁺ plasmids (UoS)

- *In vivo* models (UCM, UoS): *E. coli*/*Galleria mellonella*/AMR⁺ plasmids (UoS)
- To be decided (APHA)

Intervention strategies

- Antibiotics (IP, UCM): beta-lactams/other stresses/biocides (IP)
- To be decided (UoS)

Metagenomics studies

- 16S profiling (UCM, UoS): *in vitro* gut models (UoS)
- Deep sequencing (NVI, UCM, UoS): pig faecal samples (NVI), *in vitro* gut models (UoS)
- To be decided (APHA)

Data storage and sharing

- Data storage: in house (IP, APHA, UoS, BfR), Abel computer cluster (NVI), nucleotide databases (BfR)
- Data sharing: EJP website (APHA, UoS), to be decided (IP, NVI), specific collaborations/reports/publications/meetings (BfR)

Detailed information

Collections of isolates

Partner	Source (numbers)	Species	De-replication	Isolate selection	Focus (AMR)	Focus (MGEs)
ANSES (France)						
IP (France)	Human/National Reference Centre Human/2 different hospitals (carriage and disease)	Enterobacteriaceae: <i>E. coli</i> and <i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	Origin-dependent Also isolates from the same patient or from an outbreak		Carbapenemase and ESBL producing isolates	Plasmids (all) Transposons (their mobility)
BfR (Germany)	Healthy animals: pig, cattle, poultry (faeces) Food: meat, milk, cheese, etc.	Enterobacteriaceae: <i>E. coli</i> and <i>Klebsiella</i> spp MALDI-TOF to identify species	One isolate per sample from federal state laboratories	Columbia Blood agar and ENDO-Agar	ESBL ⁺ , carbapenemase ⁺ , flouoroquinolone and colistin resistance	Plasmids and phages carrying AMR
NVI (Norway)	Hospital/human/UTI (120) GP/human/UTI (120) Broilers/intestinal/healthy (362) Broilers/meat (141) – WGS data available	Enterobacteriaceae: <i>E. coli</i> and <i>Klebsiella</i> (very few) MALDI-TOF to identify species	Random selection of one colony per sample	MacConkey and MacConkey + cefotaxime (1 mg/L)	Random <i>E. coli</i> , ESBL/pAmpC positive and indicator <i>E. coli</i> (tetracycline resistance)	Incl and InclK plasmids

WBVR (Netherlands)						
UCM (Spain)	Human Animal Food Environmental	<i>E. coli</i> , other Enterobacteriaceae and Pasteurellaceae MALDI-TOF to identify species	No Pulse Field Gel Electrophoresis	Selective media with antibiotic pressure	ESBL ⁺ , carbapenemase ⁺ , fluoroquinolone and colistin resistance Aminoglycosides, methyltransferases	Plasmids (all)
APHA (UK)	Farm/pig faeces (400+) Farm/seagulls (15+)	<i>E. coli</i>	Source-limited: pig faecal samples combined into 30 pools (10 samples/pool) – 1-3 isolates per pool selected for WGS	CHROMagar ECC, CHROMagar ECC + ciprofloxacin (1mg/L), CHROMagar ECC + cefotaxime (1mg/L) and CHROMagar ESBL	AMR present on isolates from non-selective and selective media	No
PHE (UK)						
UoS (UK)	Hospitals/human/UTI (245) Hospital/human/blood bacteraemia (~10/month x 12 months) Hospital/human/UTI (10/month x 12 months) GP/human/UTI (10/month x 12 months) Farm/cattle/faeces/healthy (5+/month x 3 months) Farm/poultry/faeces/healthy (5+/month x 12 months) Farm/pigs/faeces/healthy (5+/month x 12 months) Vet practices/poultry/faeces/disease (47)	<i>E. coli</i> (CHROMagar Orientation and indole test to confirm species)	GTG ₅ PCR (doi:10.1111/j.1574-6968.2007.00948.x) One isolate per sample to be selected for WGS	MacConkey 3 agar, MacConkey 3 agar + cefotaxime 2 mg/L, MacConkey 3 agar + ciprofloxacin 0.5 mg/L, MacConkey 3 agar + meropenem 8 mg/L, MacConkey 3 agar + colistin 2 mg/L	ESBL ⁺ , carbapenemase ⁺ , fluoroquinolone and colistin resistance	Most prevalent AMR ⁺ plasmids

Methods of characterization

Partner	AMR profile	AMR genes	MGE type	Phylotype	Virulence genes
ANSES (France)					
IP (France)	EUCAST Kirby Bauer/E - TEST/MIC dilution	PCR/Sanger sequencing (National Reference Centre) WGS: ResFinder (CGE database)	WGS: PlasmidFinder and scripts (CGE database)	MLST (National Reference Centre, Warwick protocol) WGS: customized script (Warwick database)	WGS: not yet done
BfR (Germany)	CLSI/EUCAST MIC dilution	Multiplex PCR: qnr (Wang 2016), mcr (Liu 2015, Rebelo 2018), etc. PCR/Sanger sequencing DNA hybridisation: Guerra 2014 WGS: ResFinder (CGE database, %ID 30%, min length 20%)	PCR-based replicon typing (doi: 10.1016/j.mimet.2005.03.018) Degenerate primer MOB typing (doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0040438) WGS: PHASTER (phages, NCBI database), BlastN (NCBI database), IS Finder, Plasmid Finder (%ID 50%, min length 20%)	WGS: MLST, cgMLST, serotyping, etc. (CGE database)	WGS: Virulence Finder (CGE database, %ID 85%, min length 20%) MyDB finder (in house database, %ID 30%, min length 20%)
NVI (Norway)	EUCAST MIC dilution	Multiplex PCR: pAmpC (Perez-Perez 2002), ESBLs (Hasman 2005) PCR/Sanger sequencing: ESBL (Hasman 2005 and Briñas 2003) qPCR: CMY-2 (Schmidt 2015) WGS: ARIBA (ResFinder database)	PCR-based replicon typing (doi: 10.1016/j.mimet.2005.03.018) WGS: PlasFlow (default parameters)	Multiplex PCR (Doumith 2012) MLVA PFGE WGS: ARIBA (MLST database)	WGS: ARIBA (VirulenceFinder database)
WBVR (Netherlands)					
UCM (Spain)	EUCAST Kirby Bauer/E - TEST/MIC dilution	Multiplex PCR PCR/Sanger sequencing WGS: ARIBA (ResFinder database)	PCR-based replicon typing (doi: 10.1016/j.mimet.2005.03.018) Degenerate primer MOB typing (doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0040438) WGS: ARIBA (PlasmidFinder database)	Multiplex PCR MLST WGS: MLST (Warwick, Pasteur databases)	WGS: ARIBA (VirulenceFinder database)
APHA (UK)	EUCAST MIC dilution	WGS: Abricate/APHA SeqFinderV3 APHA AMR database	WGS: PlasmidFinder/ISFinder Default database Default parameters	WGS: MLST <i>E. coli</i> database	WGS: APHA SeqFinderV3 APHA virulence factor database

		Mlsthnorm: Ecoli K12 MG1655 alleles, Filtering: mean coverage >3, goodSnps <=30, Gaps <1		Default parameters	Mlsthnorm: Ecoli K12 MG1655 alleles, Filtering: mean coverage >3, goodSnps <=30, Gaps <1
PHE (UK)					
UoS (UK)	EUCAST Kirby Bauer/ MIC dilution	Multiplex PCR: TEM/SHV/OXA, CTX-M, AmpC (doi:10.1093/jac/dkp498), MCR (doi:10.1016/S1473-3099(15)00424-7 and 10.2807/1560-7917.ES.2016.21.27.30280). WGS: Abricate (ARGannot, CARD, NCBI, ResFinder databases)	WGS: Abricate (PlasmidFinder database)	WGS: Abricate/MS LT (EcOH database)	WGS: Abricate (Virulence Finder database)

Whole genome sequencing

Partner	Numbers	Platform	Quality control	Assembly	Annotation	Phylogeny	Pangenome analysis
ANSES (France)							
IP (France)	About 400 (all from the longitudinal studies and some from collections with different criteria)	Illumina (HiSeq and MiSeq) PacBio (few isolates)	IP pipeline	SPAdes	Prokka or RAST	ParSNP, MEGA, RAxML	Roary
BfR (Germany)	100-200 (interesting AMR determinants & combinations, PFGE profiles, plasmid sizes/diversity)	Illumina (MiSeq 2x251 bp, NextSeq 2x151 bp) PacBio	Kraken (NCBI database)	SPAdes (PATRIC database, min coverage > 15)	PGAP (NCBI database)	CSI phylogeny (CGE database, default parameters) Bionumerics	
NVI (Norway)	To be decided (around 120 + 100 from longitudinal studies, farms with repeated positive findings)	Illumina (HiSeq/MiSeq) Nanopore (few)	FastQC/multiQC	SPAdes Different kmer size	Prokka Default parameters		
WBVR (Netherlands)							
UCM (Spain)	Some	Illumina (outsourced)	FastQC, Kraken	Spades, Unicycler	Prokka	RAxML	Roary

		Nanopore (in the lab)					
APHA (UK)	500+ (all)	Illumina (NextSeq)	FastQC/ Kraken Minikraken database Default parameters	SPAdes Kmer size: 21, 33, 55, 77, 99, 127; -- careful	Prokka Default database Default parameters	Snippy/RAxML Snippy: E coli K12 MG1655 reference RAxML: PThreads, gtrgamma, corealn, 1000 bootstrap	
PHE (UK)							
UoS (UK)	96 (hospitals/UTIs) ~10x12 (hospital/blood bacteraemia) ~10x12 (hospital/UTIs) ~10x12 (GP/UTIs) ~5x12 (healthy pigs) ~5x12 (healthy chickens) ~25 (sick chickens)	Illumina Nanopore	Shovill Quast	Shovill (SPAdes)	Prokka	ParSNP Figtree	Roary

Models of transmission/fitness

Partner	Fitness studies	Transmission studies	Intervention strategies	Metagenomics studies
ANSES (France)				
IP (France)	<i>In vitro</i> models: growth and survival in different culture media, effect of antibiotics at sub-MIC concentration <i>E. coli</i>	<i>In vitro</i> models: <i>E. coli</i> isolates from different lineages and sources (human/animals) Plasmids carrying carbapenemase genes	Antibiotics (mainly beta-lactams): different concentrations for fitness studies and experimental evolution (first trial done with imipenem on an <i>E. coli</i> OXA-181*) Other stresses and biocides	No
BfR (Germany)	<i>In vitro</i> models: bacterial growth assays with and without plasmids <i>E. coli</i>	<i>In vitro</i> models: conjugation, mobilization, transposition, integration, lysogenization... <i>Enterobacteriaceae</i> (esp. <i>E. coli</i>)	No	No

	<i>mcr</i> - plasmids/phages, <i>qnr</i> - plasmids/phages	AMR plasmids and phages		
NVI (Norway)	<i>In vitro</i> models (plasmid competition experiments?) <i>E. coli</i> IncK and Incl plasmids	<i>In vitro</i> models (broth, solid, biofilm, different temperatures) <i>E. coli</i> , <i>Serratia</i> , other Enterobacteriaceae IncK and Incl plasmids	No	Deep sequencing (shotgun sequencing, read length 1x150 or 2x150 bp) Pig fecal samples Power Fecal DNA extraction Kit (MoBIO) Illumina HiSeq
WBVR (Netherlands)				
UCM (Spain)	<i>In vitro</i> models <i>In vivo</i> models	<i>In vitro</i> models <i>In vivo</i> models	Antibiotics	Yes, after 16S amplification Yes, by deep sequencing QC: FastQC Assembly: Velvet/SPAdes AMR genes: ResFinder MGEs: PlasmidFinder Statistics: RStudio
APHA (UK)	No	Yes, method to be defined	No	Maybe
PHE (UK)				
UoS (UK)	<i>In vitro</i> models: chicken and pig gut models <i>In vivo</i> models: <i>Galleria mellonella</i> <i>E. coli</i> Most prevalent AMR ⁺ plasmids	<i>In vitro</i> models: chicken and pig gut models <i>In vivo</i> models: <i>Galleria mellonella</i> <i>E. coli</i> Most prevalent AMR ⁺ plasmids	Yes, to be decided	<i>In vitro</i> chicken and pig gut models Power Fecal DNA extraction Kit (MoBIO) 16 profiling/deep sequencing

Statistics, data storage and sharing

Partner	Statistics	Data storage	Data sharing
ANSES (France)			
IP (France)	Depends on the question	Genomic data are stored as flat files (not dedicated database)	Plan to provide access to assembly files by means to be discussed
BfR (Germany)	R	In house server, nucleotide databases (i.e. Genbank - NCBI)	Specific collaborations, reports, publication, presentation on meetings, etc.
NVI (Norway)	R	Abel computer cluster (650 computers and over 10000 cores)	To be decided
WBVR (Netherlands)			
UCM (Spain)	RStudio		
APHA (UK)		In house drive	OHEJP website
PHE (UK)			
UoS (UK)		Onsite	EJP website